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EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CRM SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION IN ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT

ОЦІНКА ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ CRM-СИСТЕМ У СИСТЕМІ УПРАВЛІННЯ ПІДПРИЄМСТВОМ

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Філіппов В.Ю., Дін Сяофан, Сараєва А.О. Оцінка ефективності впровадження CRM-систем у системі управління підприємством. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті обґрунтовано теоретичні та методичні підходи до оцінки ефективності впровадження CRM-систем у системі управління підприємством в умовах цифрової трансформації. Визначено роль CRM-систем як інструменту управління клієнтськими відносинами, автоматизації бізнес-процесів і підвищення якості сервісу. Розглянуто підходи до оцінки CRM-управління на основі економічних, організаційних, маркетингових і процесних показників. Запропоновано систему кількісних показників, що включає рентабельність інвестицій, конверсію клієнтів, рівень автоматизації, продуктивність персоналу, термін окупності та інтегральний коефіцієнт ефективності. Для оцінки CRM-управління рекомендовано SWOT-, GAP-, KPI-аналіз, BI-аналітику, CRM Maturity Model та Customer Journey Map.

Ключові слова: CRM-система, цифровізація, управління клієнтськими відносинами, ефективність CRM, KPI, цифрова трансформація, бізнес-процеси, цифрова зрілість підприємства

Filippov V.Yu., Xiaofang Ding, Saraieva A.O. Evaluation of the Effectiveness of CRM System Implementation in Enterprise Management. Scientific and methodical article.

The article substantiates theoretical and methodological approaches to assessing the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise management under conditions of digital transformation. The role of CRM systems as a tool for customer relationship management, business process automation, and service quality improvement is defined. Approaches to evaluating CRM management based on economic, organizational, marketing, and process indicators are considered. A system of quantitative indicators is proposed, including return on investment, customer conversion, level of business process automation, staff productivity, payback period, and an integrated efficiency coefficient. SWOT analysis, GAP analysis, KPI analysis, BI analytics, CRM Maturity Model, and Customer Journey Map are recommended as analytical tools for evaluating CRM management.

Keywords: CRM system, digitalization, customer relationship management, CRM effectiveness, KPI, digital transformation, business processes, enterprise digital maturity

Under the conditions of the digital transformation of the economy and increasing competition, enterprises are increasingly implementing CRM systems as a tool for automating customer relationship management, improving business process efficiency, and enhancing the quality of customer service.

The digitalization of CRM processes is of particular importance for enterprises in the service and logistics sectors, whose activities directly depend on the speed of information processing, coordination of interaction between departments, and the effectiveness of communication with clients.

At the same time, the implementation of CRM systems does not guarantee an automatic increase in enterprise performance efficiency. In practice, the effectiveness of CRM solutions largely depends on the level of enterprise digital maturity, the quality of information system integration, personnel readiness for digital changes, and management's ability to use analytical tools for managerial decision-making. In this regard, there is a need to develop a comprehensive approach to evaluating the effectiveness of CRM system implementation that would take into account not only the financial results of digitalization, but also the organizational, process, and customer-related aspects of enterprise functioning.

The insufficient level of methodological support for evaluating CRM management effectiveness, the fragmented use of analytical indicators, and the absence of a unified approach to the comprehensive analysis of CRM system performance determine the relevance of studying the theoretical and practical aspects of evaluating the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise management.

Analysis of recent publications on the problem

The issues of enterprise management digitalization, implementation of CRM and ERP systems, business process automation, and evaluation of the effectiveness of digital solutions are actively studied by both domestic and foreign scholars. Modern scientific publications pay considerable attention to the problems of enterprise digital transformation, the development of customer-oriented management models, the use of analytical data processing tools, and the implementation of digital technologies in business process management systems.

Domestic studies are mainly focused on the adaptation of CRM and ERP systems to the specific features of Ukrainian enterprises, the evaluation of business process digitalization effectiveness, management automation, and the impact of digital technologies on enterprise performance. Considerable attention is paid to the issues of information system integration, improving customer relationship management efficiency, enterprise digital maturity, and logistics process optimization.

Foreign scientific studies are more focused on the strategic aspects of digital transformation, the use of artificial intelligence, predictive analytics, BI systems, and big data processing technologies in enterprise management systems. Particular attention is given to issues of business digital resilience, enterprise adaptation to changes in the market environment, the development of personnel digital competencies, and the use of data analytics to support managerial decision-making.

The scientific studies related to the topic of the article can be conditionally grouped into three main categories.

The first group includes studies devoted to CRM and ERP systems, their functioning, implementation features, and evaluation of their effectiveness at enterprises: Yurchuk N.P. [2], Hanushchak-Yefimenko L.M. [3], Pylypenko L.M., & Redko M.O. [4], Kurhan N.V. [5], and Lysenko O.A., & Lysenko V.V. [6].

The second group consists of studies related to business process digitalization, the development of enterprise information infrastructure, digital transformation, and optimization of management processes: Lazebnyk L.L., & Voitenko V.O. [7], Kalach H.M., & Zub P.V. [8], Lazebnyk L.L. [9], Tkachuk H.Yu., & Biliak T.O. [10], Lutsenko I.S., & Konovalova I.V. [11], and Filippov V.Yu., & Antoshchuk V.M. [16].

The third group covers foreign studies devoted to the use of digital technologies, artificial intelligence, data analytics, and enterprise digital resilience under modern conditions: Ellingrud K., Sanghvi S., Dandona G.S., Madgavkar A., Chui M., White O., & Hasebe P. [12], Hazan E., Madgavkar A., Chui M., Smit S., Maor D., Dandona G.S., & Huyghues-Despointes R. [13], Lund S., Madgavkar A., & Manyika J. [14], and Iftikhar A., Ali I., Arslan A., & Tarba S. [15].

The conducted analysis of scientific sources indicates a high level of scientific interest in the issues of enterprise management digitalization and CRM system implementation. At the same time, the issues related to the formation of a comprehensive approach to evaluating CRM management effectiveness, which would combine economic, process, customer-oriented, and strategic indicators for assessing the effectiveness of enterprise digital transformation, remain insufficiently studied.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem

Despite the significant number of scientific studies devoted to the digitalization of customer relationship management and the implementation of CRM systems, the issues of comprehensive evaluation of CRM management effectiveness under the conditions of enterprise digital transformation remain insufficiently studied. Most scientific approaches are mainly focused on analyzing the economic effect of business process automation, while the organizational, process, and customer-oriented aspects of CRM system functioning are often considered fragmentarily.

Further scientific substantiation is required for the formation of an integrated system of indicators for evaluating CRM system effectiveness, which would combine financial KPIs, indicators of enterprise digital maturity, customer service assessment, and analytical tools of strategic management. The practical aspects of applying modern CRM management analysis methods for enterprises in the service and logistics sectors also remain insufficiently studied, as their activities are characterized by a high dependence on the speed of information interaction, process coordination, and the quality of communication with clients.

Formulation of research objectives (task setting)

The aim of the article is to substantiate theoretical and methodological approaches to evaluating the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise management under the conditions of the digital transformation of the economy, as well as to develop a comprehensive approach to analyzing the effectiveness of CRM management based on economic, process, organizational, and customer-oriented indicators.

To achieve the stated purpose, the following objectives were defined in the article:

- to investigate the essence and role of CRM systems in the digital enterprise management system;
- to generalize modern approaches to evaluating the effectiveness of CRM management;
- to identify the main indicators for assessing the effectiveness of CRM system implementation;
- to systematize methods and analytical tools for evaluating CRM management effectiveness;
- to substantiate the expediency of using a comprehensive approach to evaluating the effectiveness of customer relationship management digitalization;
- to determine prospective directions for the further development of CRM system effectiveness evaluation systems in enterprise activities.

As a result of the study, all the defined objectives were fully achieved, and the overall result of the research was the formation of a comprehensive approach to evaluating the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise management based on the combination of economic, organizational, process, and customer-oriented indicators, as well as modern analytical tools of digital management.

Materials and methods

The study employed general scientific and special research methods. The methods of theoretical generalization and system analysis were used to investigate the essence of CRM systems and their role in enterprise management. Methods of comparative analysis, classification, and systematization were applied to generalize approaches to evaluating CRM management effectiveness and to develop a system of indicators for assessing CRM system performance. The methodological basis of the study includes KPI analysis, SWOT analysis, GAP analysis, CRM Maturity Model, BI analytics, and other tools for evaluating the digitalization of business processes. The information base of the study consists of scientific publications, analytical materials, and open sources related to digital transformation and CRM management.

Presentation of main results and their justification

Under the conditions of enterprise digital transformation, the implementation of CRM systems is considered not only as a technological modernization of business processes, but also as a strategic tool for improving the efficiency of customer relationship management [1, 7]. At the same time, the effectiveness of CRM solutions largely depends on the enterprise's ability to assess their impact on operational activities, financial results, service quality, and the effectiveness of interaction with clients.

In scientific research, the issue of evaluating CRM system effectiveness is considered comprehensively through economic, organizational, marketing, and managerial indicators. Modern approaches to evaluating CRM management involve the analysis not only of the financial effect of process automation, but also of changes in customer loyalty, request processing speed, communication quality, and the effectiveness of managerial decision-making [6, 10, 11].

The generalization of theoretical approaches makes it possible to identify the main directions for evaluating CRM management effectiveness:

- economic efficiency;
- operational efficiency;
- marketing efficiency;
- customer service efficiency;
- business process management efficiency;
- the level of enterprise digital integration.

One of the most common approaches is the assessment of the economic effect of CRM system implementation. This approach is based on the analysis of changes in the enterprise's financial indicators after the automation of customer relationship management processes [7, 15].

The main indicators include return on investment, sales growth, cost reduction, labor productivity, and project payback period. Along with financial indicators, non-financial evaluation criteria are also of significant importance, since the CRM system directly affects the quality of customer service and the internal organization of business processes. Under modern conditions, the effectiveness of CRM management is largely determined by the enterprise's ability to promptly process information, coordinate interaction between departments, and ensure personalized work with clients.

To ensure a comprehensive and objective evaluation of the effectiveness of customer relationship management digitalization, it is advisable to analyze CRM system effectiveness through three interconnected directions: the system of main indicators for evaluating enterprise CRM management effectiveness, the system of indicators for evaluating CRM system implementation effectiveness, and the use of modern methods and tools for evaluating enterprise CRM management effectiveness. Such an approach makes it possible to combine the assessment of the economic effect of digitalization, the level of business process automation, the effectiveness of customer interaction, the efficiency of managerial decisions, and the level of enterprise digital maturity. The integrated use of quantitative indicators, KPIs, strategic analysis methods, and analytical tools provides the opportunity to form well-grounded conclusions regarding the feasibility of CRM system implementation, the selection of an optimal digital solution, and the determination of directions for the further development of the enterprise management system. At the same time, the combination of these approaches creates prerequisites for the timely identification of problematic aspects of digitalization, assessment of the level of business process adaptation to the digital environment, and improvement of the efficiency of customer data usage in managerial decision-making.

Such a comprehensive approach is of particular importance for enterprises in the service, logistics, and freight forwarding sectors, where operational efficiency largely depends on the speed of information interaction, the quality of customer service, the coordination of internal processes, and the enterprise's ability to promptly respond to changes in the market environment [10, 15]. It is the comprehensive combination of financial, process-oriented, customer-oriented, and strategic analysis tools that makes it possible to form a holistic understanding of the level of enterprise CRM management effectiveness and the prospects for its further digital transformation.

To evaluate the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise activities, it is advisable to use a system of quantitative indicators and analytical metrics (Table 1).

Table 1. Main Indicators for Evaluating the Effectiveness of Enterprise CRM Management

Indicator	Calculation Formula	Indicator Characteristics	Practical Significance
Return on Investment in CRM (ROI CRM)	$ROI = \frac{\text{Add. Prof.} - \text{CRM Costs}}{\text{CRM Costs}} \times 100\%$	Determines the economic efficiency of CRM implementation	Assessment of digitalization payback
Sales Growth Rate	$T_{s-s} = \frac{S-s \text{ Vol.}_{\text{aft.}} - S-s \text{ Vol.}_{\text{bef.}}}{S-s \text{ Volume}_{\text{bef.}}} \times 100\%$	Shows changes in sales volumes	Assessment of CRM impact on revenue
Customer Retention Rate	$R = \frac{\# \text{ of Regular Customers}}{\text{Total \# of Customers}} \times 100\%$	Determines the level of customer base retention	Assessment of customer loyalty
Request Processing Speed	$T_{\text{op}} = \frac{\text{Total Processing Time}}{\text{Number of Requests}}$	Reflects operational efficiency	Analysis of business process efficiency
Manager Productivity	$P = \frac{\text{Number of Deals}}{\text{Number of Managers}}$	Assesses personnel performance	Monitoring work efficiency
Process Automation Level	$A = \frac{\text{Automated Processes}}{\text{Total Number of Processes}} \times 100\%$	Characterizes the level of digitalization	Assessment of digital maturity
Customer Acquisition Cost (CAC)	$CAC = \frac{\text{Marketing Costs}}{\text{Number of New Customers}}$	Determines customer acquisition costs	Analysis of marketing efficiency
Average Revenue per Customer (ARPC)	$ARPC = \frac{\text{Total Revenue}}{\text{Number of Customers}}$	Determines average customer profitability	Assessment of customer base value
Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI)	$CSI = \frac{\sum \text{Customer Ratings}}{\text{Number of Respondents}}$	Characterizes service quality level	Analysis of service quality
Conversion Rate	$\text{Conversion} = \frac{\text{Number of Deals}}{\text{Number of Requests}} \times 100\%$	Determines sales effectiveness	Analysis of interaction efficiency

Source: elaborated by the author based on [2, 3, 7, 8, 10, 11, 15]

The presented indicators make it possible to comprehensively assess the impact of a CRM system on enterprise activities and can be used both for internal efficiency monitoring and for strategic analysis of digitalization results.

In modern practice, the evaluation of CRM management effectiveness is increasingly carried out using an integrated approach that combines financial, process, and customer-related indicators. Such an approach makes it possible to assess not only the direct economic effect of automation, but also the quality of enterprise interaction with clients, the level of digital integration, and the degree of business process adaptation to the conditions of the digital economy.

An important direction in evaluating CRM system effectiveness is also the analysis of the enterprise's level of digital maturity. Digital maturity characterizes the enterprise's readiness to use modern digital technologies, integrate information systems, and automate management processes. From a practical perspective, a high level of digital maturity ensures:

- faster adaptation to market changes;
- increased management flexibility;
- improved coordination between departments;
- reduced decision-making time;
- more efficient use of customer data.

A separate role in modern CRM management is played by analytical tools, business intelligence (BI) systems, artificial intelligence technologies, and predictive analytics. Their use enables enterprises to automate customer behavior analysis, forecast demand, identify customer churn risks, and create personalized commercial offers.

Along with the advantages of CRM system implementation, the process of digitalizing customer relationship management is accompanied by certain risks and limitations. The main ones include:

- significant financial costs of implementation;
- complexity of integration with existing systems;
- information security risks;
- insufficient level of personnel digital competencies;
- organizational resistance to change;

— dependence on the quality and completeness of data.

The effectiveness of enterprise CRM management is determined not only by the fact of CRM system implementation, but primarily by the enterprise's ability to integrate digital technologies into the business process management system and ensure their effective use [8, 15]. The application of a system of quantitative indicators and analytical metrics makes it possible to assess the level of effectiveness of customer relationship management digitalization and form the basis for further analysis of enterprise activities.

The presented theoretical approaches and indicators for evaluating CRM management effectiveness can be used in further research for analyzing the customer relationship management system of LLC "Expeditor", assessing the level of business process digitalization of the enterprise, and substantiating directions for improving CRM management.

To evaluate the effectiveness of CRM system implementation, it is advisable to use a system of quantitative indicators that make it possible to assess the economic, organizational, and managerial effects of business process digitalization at the enterprise (Table 2).

Table 2. Main Indicators for Evaluating the Effectiveness of CRM System Implementation

Indicator	Formula	Indicator Characteristics	Designation
Time Saving	$E_t = (T_1 - T_2) \times N$	Determines the reduction of time costs after business process automation	T_1 – time required to perform operations before CRM implementation; T_2 – time after CRM implementation; N – number of operations
Customer Conversion	$K = \frac{C}{L} \times 100\%$	Efficiency of converting inquiries into actual customers	C – number of successful deals; L – number of leads (inquiries)
Return on Investment (ROI)	$ROI = \frac{P - C}{C} \times 100\%$	Economic efficiency of CRM system implementation	P – profit generated by CRM; C – implementation costs
Payback Period	$PP = \frac{C}{CF}$	Shows the period required to recover investments in the CRM system	C – CRM costs; CF – cash flow generated from CRM usage
Automation Coefficient	$K_a = AP \times 100\%$	Reflects the level of business process automation at the enterprise	AP – share of automated processes
Integrated Efficiency Coefficient	$K_e = \frac{\sum E_i}{n}$	Summarizes the average growth of key performance indicators	E_i – growth of a particular indicator; n – number of indicators

Source: elaborated by the author based on [2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 16]

The use of analytical indicators provides the opportunity for a comprehensive study of CRM management effectiveness, determination of the level of process automation, evaluation of personnel productivity, and analysis of the impact of digital technologies on the efficiency of customer interaction.

The application of the presented indicators enables an enterprise to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the effectiveness of CRM process digitalization, assess the level of economic effect from automation, monitor personnel performance efficiency, and formulate well-grounded managerial decisions regarding the further development of the customer relationship management system.

In the practice of CRM system evaluation, the most commonly used indicators are time savings, customer conversion, return on investment, payback period, the level of business process automation, and the integrated efficiency coefficient [7, 15]. These indicators make it possible to quantitatively assess the effectiveness of CRM solution implementation and may be used in further studies of enterprise activities.

For a comprehensive evaluation of enterprise CRM management effectiveness, modern practice uses not only financial indicators and KPIs, but also strategic and analytical methods for studying business processes. Such tools make it possible to assess the level of enterprise digital maturity, identify problematic aspects of customer relationship management, and determine directions for further CRM system improvement.

Modern approaches to evaluating CRM management effectiveness are based on the combination of strategic, process-oriented, and customer-oriented analysis. Unlike the traditional evaluation of information systems, where the main focus was placed only on the economic effect of automation, modern CRM approaches involve a comprehensive study of both internal business processes and the effectiveness of customer interaction. In this regard, strategic analysis methods, digital maturity assessment tools, customer segmentation models, business process analytics, and key performance indicator monitoring systems are used to evaluate CRM system effectiveness. The application of a comprehensive approach enables an enterprise not only to assess the current level of CRM management effectiveness, but also to determine directions for further digital transformation, identify problematic aspects of customer relationship management, and formulate strategic priorities for enterprise development under the conditions of the digital economy (Table 3).

Table 3. Methods and Tools for Evaluating the Effectiveness of Enterprise CRM Management

Method / Tool	Essence of the Method	Direction of Application in CRM Management	Practical Significance
SWOT Analysis	Analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats	Assessment of internal and external factors of the CRM system	Determination of strategic directions for improvement
PEST Analysis	Analysis of political, economic, social, and technological factors	Assessment of the external digital environment	Analysis of the impact of market digitalization
GAP Analysis	Identification of the gap between the current and desired state	Analysis of the level of CRM process digitalization	Formation of development directions
BSC (Balanced Scorecard)	System of balanced indicators	Integration of financial and non-financial KPIs	Comprehensive efficiency evaluation
ABC Customer Analysis	Distribution of customers according to profitability level	Customer base segmentation	Identification of key customers
XYZ Customer Analysis	Assessment of demand stability and customer activity	Analysis of customer behavior	Interaction forecasting
Customer Journey Map	Visualization of the customer journey	Analysis of customer touchpoints	Improvement of customer service
CRM Maturity Model	Assessment of CRM digital maturity level	Determination of CRM system development level	Digital transformation planning
Process Mapping	Modeling of business processes	Analysis of interaction between departments	Identification of inefficient processes
BI Analytics	Real-time data analysis	Monitoring of sales and customer activity	Support of managerial decision-making
Cohort Analysis	Analysis of customer group behavior over time	Evaluation of customer retention	Loyalty forecasting
NPS (Net Promoter Score)	Assessment of customer willingness to recommend the company	Analysis of customer satisfaction	Evaluation of service quality

Source: authors' own elaboration

This is particularly relevant for enterprises in the service and logistics sectors, where operational efficiency directly depends on the speed of information interaction, process coordination, and the quality of communication with clients. The generalization of scientific approaches makes it possible to identify the main methods for analyzing the effectiveness of enterprise CRM management.

The use of the mentioned tools enables enterprises to move from intuitive customer relationship management to a systematic analytical approach. Of particular importance is the combination of strategic analysis methods with digital data processing tools, which provides the opportunity to respond promptly to changes in customer behavior and the market environment. For enterprises in the freight forwarding sector, the most relevant tools are SWOT analysis, ABC-XYZ customer segmentation, Customer Journey Map, and KPI analysis of CRM processes, since they make it possible to assess the effectiveness of interaction with customers, the speed of request processing, the stability of the customer base, and the level of digitalization of operational activities.

Under the modern conditions of the digital economy, effective CRM management increasingly depends on the enterprise's ability to use a comprehensive approach to evaluating the effectiveness of digital solutions by combining financial indicators, business process analytics, customer experience assessment, and strategic analysis tools.

Therefore, the combination of the system of main indicators for evaluating enterprise CRM management effectiveness, indicators for assessing the effectiveness of CRM system implementation, as well as modern methods and tools for CRM management analysis, makes it possible to form a comprehensive approach to evaluating the effectiveness of customer relationship management digitalization. The use of an integrated approach provides the opportunity to take into account the economic, organizational, process-oriented, and customer-oriented aspects of enterprise functioning, assess the level of digital maturity, the effectiveness of business processes, and the efficiency of customer data usage.

The comprehensive application of quantitative indicators, KPIs, strategic analysis methods, and analytical tools creates the basis for making well-grounded managerial decisions regarding the feasibility of CRM system implementation, the selection of an optimal CRM solution, and the determination of priority directions for further enterprise digital transformation. This makes it possible to minimize the risks of digitalization, improve the effectiveness of customer relationship management, and ensure a long-term increase in enterprise competitiveness.

Conclusions and prospects for further research

The studied theoretical and methodological aspects of evaluating the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise management under the conditions of the digital transformation of the economy make it possible to establish that modern CRM systems act not only as tools for business process automation, but also as comprehensive elements of enterprise digital management that ensure improved efficiency of customer interaction, optimization of internal processes, and enhancement of managerial decision-making quality. As a result of the study, modern approaches to evaluating CRM management effectiveness based on the combination

of economic, organizational, marketing, and process indicators were generalized. It was determined that the evaluation of CRM system effectiveness requires the use of a comprehensive approach that takes into account not only the direct financial effect of automation, but also the level of enterprise digital maturity, the effectiveness of customer service, personnel productivity, the speed of information interaction, and the quality of business process management.

A system of the main indicators for evaluating CRM system effectiveness was developed, including indicators of return on investment, customer conversion, payback period, process automation level, personnel productivity, and the integrated efficiency coefficient. The expediency of using modern analytical tools and strategic analysis methods, including SWOT analysis, GAP analysis, KPI analysis, BI analytics, CRM Maturity Model, and Customer Journey Map, was substantiated, as these tools make it possible to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of enterprise CRM process digitalization.

It was proven that the highest effectiveness of CRM systems is achieved under the conditions of integrating digital technologies into the overall enterprise management system, adapting business processes to the digital environment, and ensuring the systematic use of customer data in managerial decision-making. At the same time, it was established that an insufficient level of personnel digital competencies, fragmentation of digital infrastructure, organizational resistance to change, and problems with information system integration can significantly reduce the effectiveness of CRM solution implementation.

The practical significance of the obtained results lies in the possibility of using the proposed indicators, methods, and analytical tools to assess the feasibility of CRM system implementation, determine the level of effectiveness of customer relationship management digitalization, and formulate directions for the further development of the enterprise management system.

Prospects for further scientific research should be associated with the development of integrated models for assessing the digital maturity of CRM management, the adaptation of artificial intelligence technologies and predictive analytics to customer relationship management systems, as well as the study of the peculiarities of CRM process digitalization in various sectors of the economy, particularly in logistics, freight forwarding activities, and the service business.

Abstract

The article examines the theoretical and methodological aspects of evaluating the effectiveness of CRM system implementation in enterprise management under conditions of the digital transformation of the economy. The relevance of the study is determined by the active spread of digital technologies in business process management, the growing role of customer-oriented approaches in enterprise management, and the need to improve the efficiency of customer interaction in conditions of increasing competition. The issue of evaluating CRM system performance is particularly important for enterprises operating in the service, logistics, and freight forwarding sectors, where operational efficiency directly depends on the speed of information exchange, the level of business process automation, and the quality of customer service.

The study identifies the role of CRM systems as a strategic tool of digital enterprise management that ensures the automation of customer relationship management processes, optimization of internal business processes, increased personnel productivity, and improvement of managerial decision-making quality. Modern approaches to assessing CRM management effectiveness based on economic, organizational, marketing, and process indicators are considered. Particular attention is paid to integrated approaches for evaluating CRM system performance that combine financial KPIs, indicators of enterprise digital maturity, customer behavior analytics, and strategic analysis tools.

A system of quantitative indicators for evaluating CRM system effectiveness is proposed, including indicators of return on investment, customer conversion, payback period, level of business process automation, personnel productivity, application processing speed, and integrated efficiency coefficient. A comprehensive set of modern methods and analytical tools for CRM management evaluation has been developed, including SWOT analysis, GAP analysis, KPI analysis, BI analytics, CRM Maturity Model, Customer Journey Map, ABC-XYZ customer analysis, and Process Mapping. The study proves that the effectiveness of CRM system implementation is determined not only by the level of business process automation, but also by the enterprise's ability to integrate digital technologies into the overall management system, adapt business processes to the digital environment, and ensure the systematic use of customer data for managerial decision-making. It has been established that the comprehensive combination of financial, process-oriented, customer-oriented, and strategic approaches to evaluating CRM management performance creates the foundation for improving enterprise digitalization efficiency, minimizing the risks of implementing digital solutions, and ensuring long-term growth in enterprise competitiveness.

The practical significance of the obtained results lies in the possibility of applying the proposed system of indicators, analytical methods, and evaluation tools for assessing the feasibility of CRM system implementation, determining the effectiveness of enterprise digitalization, and improving customer relationship management processes. The proposed approaches may be used by enterprises of various sectors of the economy, particularly in the fields of services, logistics, and transport-forwarding activities, for the development of effective digital transformation strategies and the enhancement of enterprise competitiveness in the digital economy.

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